

Project Number: 101077369
Project Acronym: REDI4Heat
Project title: RED Implementation of Heating and Cooling

Progress Report

Period covered by the report
from M1 [01/10/2022] to M8 [31/05/2023]

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1. Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and Overview of the progress

Description of the work carried out during the reporting period in line with the Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement.

- **Overview** of the project results towards the objective of the action in line with the structure of the Annex 1

As an overview, the project results are in line with the Grant Agreement and with the structure of the Annex 1 in the Description of the Action.

- **Summary** of deliverables and milestones

The deliverables and milestones prepared and submitted for the referring period are shown in the tables below.

Table 1: List of Deliverables M1-M9

WP	Name	Leader	Deadline	Status
WP1	D1.2 – Technical progress report	CRES	M9	submitted
WP6	D6.1 – Communication & Dissemination plan	EHPA	M6	submitted
WP7	D7.1 – SE&R plan	ADENE	M9	submitted

Table 2: List of Milestones M1-M9

WP	Name	Leader	Deadline	Status
WP1	1 - Consortium Agreement	CRES	M2	submitted
WP1	2 - Environmental Footprint Guide	CRES	M4	submitted
WP1	3 - Data and Ethics Report	CRES	M6	submitted
WP6	18 - Online presence	EHPA	M6	submitted
WP7	22 - NSGs and EAB constituted	ADENE	M9	submitted

- **Summary** of exploitable results with an explanation about how they can/will be exploited.

The key exploitable results (KERs) are described in detail in the D7.1 SE&R Plan, submitted in M9. In summary, the KERs include the following outcomes:

- NECP Assessment Guideline (D 3.3, due in M24), aimed at supporting the identification of the H&C decarbonisation key drivers, missing elements, weaknesses and strengths;
- Knowledge sharing platform (T4.2, due in M25), will be developed with the main propose of making publicly available the heat transition toolbox (comprising resources from REDI4Heat and previous and ongoing initiatives). It will be available online, in the REDI4Heat website;
- Policy Adoption Scenarios & Measures for the Decarbonization of the Heating and Cooling Sector (D 4.1 and D 4.2, due in M23 and M34, respectively), will be developed in the framework of WP4 and includes a compilation of the policies in place and other policies and strategies for the decarbonization of the H&C sector and effective measures for the uptake of RH&C policies at the local, regional and national levels;
- Capacity building resources (T4.3, due in M32), will be produced within WP4 and consist of transversal materials that are adapted and translated into national realities. It will be made available in the knowledge sharing platform as a way to foster the replication of these events in other MS.

The next table summarizes the KERs and the exploitation strategy/channels that will be used.

KER #	Name	Exploitation method / channels	Current status
KER 1	NECP Assessment Guideline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▫ High level meetings with European entities; ▫ Benefit from the EAB network; ▫ Mapping of related partnerships and projects with whom to have bilateral discussions; ▫ Joint initiatives involving related partnerships and projects and also non-directly related (other sectors); ▫ Connection with CA's (buildings and renewables) to present the project findings at the discussion forums; ▫ Address non-participating MS, organizing online seminars. 	Under definition (starting from M10)
KER 2	Knowledge Sharing Platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▫ Available via the REDI4Heat website; ▫ All the above mentioned points for the KER 1. 	Under definition (starting from M16)
KER 3	Policy Adoption Scenarios & Measures for the Decarbonization of the Heating and Cooling Sector	All the above mentioned points for the KER 1.	Under definition (starting from M16)
KER 4	Capacity Building Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▫ Available via the REDI4Heat website / knowledge sharing platform; ▫ All the above mentioned points for the KER 1. 	Under definition (starting from M18)

1.1. Objectives

List the specific objectives for the project as described in section 1.2 of the DoA and described the work carried out during the reporting period towards the achievement of each listed objective. Provide clear and measurable details.

1.1.1. *Establish a dialogue between the Renewable Heating and Cooling (RHC) industry and energy agencies, DSOs, local authorities and one-stop-shops building a better & common understanding of the optimal structure of incentive schemes for RHC systems, including aspects such as the development of the comprehensive assessments, training needs, etc.*

This topic is currently relevant for WP2, WP5 and WP7.

For WP2: WP2 is covering mainly the assessment of the heating and cooling strategies by the target MS.

- Work in progress on NREAPs (2020 targets)
- Work in progress for the 2030 goals and proposed measures (NECPs). New round of NECPs submitted in June 2023, to be analysed.
- Work in progress for the analysis of the national heat demand for heating and cooling, based on the national comprehensive assessments.

For WP5:

- Dialogue with RHC stakeholders and relevant legislators has been carried out until now mainly through a webinar meant to update on the status of discussions on the relevant renewable heating and cooling solutions contained in the Fit for 55 package.
- Continuous exchange with partners representing energy agencies was taking place in order to monitor the developments of the new NECPs draft, in coordination with other WPs.

For WP7:

- The NSG's, constituted within T 7.3 are composed by relevant national stakeholders in the H&C sector, including market associations, policy agents and public authorities. The 1st of these meetings, three to cover the whole project, has already taken place. These consist of discussion forums, that contribute to promote the dialogue between all the actors involved, uncovering the main concerns and challenges when addressing renewable H&C within the national contexts, as well as including the debate on the project expectations and the most relevant initiatives (namely training and competences needs) the project can provide to support the energy transition of the H&C sector.
- The European Advisory Board (EAB) was also constituted within T 7.3 and integrates a group of 10 to 12 EU experts (in total, 5 are members of the each of the NSG's). The 1st meeting of the EAB is planned for the beginning of M10 and the most relevant conclusions of the debate between the RH&C experts will be reported in the next PR. Nevertheless, the EAB meeting agenda will be aligned with the topics already discussed in the NSG's meetings

1.1.2. Evaluate the national framework regarding RES heat deployment in each MS, identifying existing studies, tools, existing infrastructure and supporting actions and mapping National Energy sources and potential for the heating and cooling sector.

This topic is currently relevant for WP2, WP3 and WP7.

For WP2: WP2 is covering mainly the assessment of the heating and cooling strategies by the target MS.

- Work on the available comprehensive assessments
- Desk research on available literature produced by RHC-ETIP and other projects

For WP3: A data collection template is being prepared where all organisations will be asked to provide inputs to verify/identify key national policies, studies and support instruments.

For WP7: The representatives of the NSG's played an import role regarding mapping/gathering the existing information to support an accurate evaluation of the current framework in the participating MS, regarding energy and renewable energy policies, RES-H&C technologies and the H&C sector in general.

1.1.3. Define adoption scenarios for renewable heating and cooling solutions, including the integration with Energy communities' scenarios, addressing energy poverty mitigation, including dedicated support on the access to renewable heating and cooling solutions for energy poor.

This topic is currently relevant for WP2 and WP7.

For WP2: The project is still in its initial stage, with most of the work consisting of analysis, being carried out mainly in line with WP2. The contribution to the goal above will come in sequence to the initial analysis done in WP2, namely in WP3 and WP4.

For WP7: The debate promoted during the 1st meetings of the NSG's already addressed several of these topics (i.e., energy poverty mitigation; the role played by the energy communities in the scenario of accelerating the integration of renewables in the H&C sector, among others). These inputs will be relevant for the completion of one of the main outcomes of WP4, related with the definition of the policy adoption scenarios for the decarbonisation of the H&C sector in the participating MS.

1.1.4. Assist public authorities in structuring planning, monitoring and reporting initiatives and enhancing policy and stakeholders' engagement, and build capacity at local level.

This topic is currently relevant for WP2 and WP7.

For WP2: The project is still in its initial stage, with most of the work consisting of analysis, being carried out mainly in line with WP2. The contribution to the goal above will come in sequence to the initial analysis done in WP2, namely in WP3 and WP4. Contacts were also organised at national level as part of WP2, regarding heating and cooling mapping.

For WP7: Some of the members in the NSG's are public authorities, namely responsible for the definition and implementation of the NECPs. The NSGs network will support the customization of some of the tools developed in WP3 and put in force in WP4, as well as promote the capacity building sessions foreseen.

1.1.5. Propose policy measures to explore the potential of RHC in Europe until 2030, taking into account market conditions, technological potential, legislative and regulatory framework and provide recommendations for improved sustainable RHC integrated support schemes.

This topic is currently relevant for WP2, WP5 and WP7.

For WP2: The project is still in its initial stage, gathering information and preparing structured analysis on market conditions, technological potential, legislative and regulatory framework.

For WP5: in preparation of the drafting of D5.1 Report containing policy briefs and recommendation, the partners involved started to analyse new relevant RED and EED provisions with the aim to assess their strengths and weaknesses towards the exploitation of RHC potential. This analysis will serve as a basis to propose policy recommendations once also gaps and opportunities of the NECPs redrafting will be assessed.

For WP7: Already in the initial discussions of the NSGs some of the challenges faced at the national level were identified and discussed. These should be the supporting ground for the definition of the National Policy Adoption Scenario for the Decarbonization of the Heating and Cooling Sector within WP4.

1.1.6. Support Member States in the assessment of the potential of using energy from renewable sources and of the use of waste heat and cold in the heating and cooling sector including: analysis of priority segments suitable for their deployment at low ecological and economic risk, analysis of the potential for large deployment of small-scale household projects, set out milestones and measures to increase renewables in heating and cooling and, where appropriate, the use of waste heat and cold through district heating and cooling, with a view of establishing and/or improving long-term national strategies to decarbonise heating and cooling.

This topic is currently relevant for WP2 and WP7.

For WP2: The project is still in its initial stage, gathering information and preparing structured analysis on market conditions, technological potential, legislative and regulatory framework.

For WP7: The representatives of the NSGs are key players in the H&C sector and can support the gathering of data and definition of scenarios that robust the national assessments. Also, the EU experts participating in the EAB will be key players on this regard and in the definition of new policies aimed at accelerating the integration of renewables in the H&C sector and contributing for the fulfilment of the new targets defined for the renewables sector.

1.1.7. Plan the Implementation of upcoming provisions in RED III

For WP2: A short update on the stages of RED III can be shown below. REDI4Heat is following these developments.

1. **14/07/2021:** EC proposal
2. **18/05/2022:** EC amendments on permitting (RED4)
3. **14/09/2022:** EP vote on RED3
4. **06/10/2022:** Trilogue start
5. **14/12/2022:** EP vote on RED4
6. **29/03/2023:** Trilogue provisional agreement
7. **28/06/2023:** ITRE vote on provisional agreement

Figure 1: Timeline for the RED revision

Article	Target
Art. 3 – Overall RES	42.5% (binding) + 2.5% (indicative)
Art. 23 – RES in H&C	+0.8 percentage points 2021-25, +1.1 2026-30 (binding)
Art. 24 – RES in DHC	+2.2 percentage points 2021-30 (indicative)
Art. 15a – RES in buildings	49% (indicative)
Art. 22a – RES in industry	+1.6 percentage points 2021-25, 2026-30 (indicative)
Artt. 15c, 16c, ... - Permitting	Renewable acceleration areas (RAAs), accelerated permitting for solar techs, ...
Artt. 28, 29 .. - Bioenergy	Stronger sustainability criteria for bioenergy Application of the cascading principle

Figure 2: Trialogue Agreement – key provisions for heating and cooling

For WP5: since M2, WP5 partners have been monitoring the trialogue discussions regarding RED III, with a specific focus on the articles concerning RES and the local dimension. This work translated in excel tables for internal use to keep track of the different versions proposed by the Commission, PE and Council together with compromise amendments. This gave the partners an early overall idea of the measures that would have probably end up in the final version of RED III, allowing some early comparison with the relevant national legislation analysed in other WPs.

For WP7: The NSGs are excellent forums to discuss the challenges and opportunities brought by RED III. During the 1st meeting of the NSG's the stakeholders had a first glimpse on the current scenario regarding the RED revision, as well as the upcoming steps. Having all the experts in the same page, regarding the RED revision, for sure will contribute to define a better strategy/method to plan the implementation of the RED III.

1.2. Explanation of the work carried per WP

Explain the work carried out in WPs and Tasks during the reporting period giving details of the work carried out per Task and involved partners. It is good to have some details on partners' work and their input. Because the partners will declare PMs for each WP, it would be good to have short summary of their contribution.

1.2.1. Work Package 1 Project Management and Coordination

The description is given analytically per task.

- **Task 1.1 – Project Management**

During M1 – M8, the project management approach has been set up and presented to the partners in the kick off meeting. The project management activities that have been implemented during M1 and M8 and will continue until the end of the project are listed below:

- Monitoring and management of project finances.
 - Submission of the Consortium Agreement
 - Monitoring and management of time plan: An analytic Time Plan of all required submissions has been presented in the kick off meeting and agreed by the Consortium.
 - Establishment of a clear decision-making process; The Steering Committee has been set up, with clear and coherent role. The responsibilities of the partners, in Tasks and Work Packages, have been clearly defined.
 - Monitoring of the project progress and mitigation of any issue; Relevant measures have been already taken to submit all deliverables and milestones not only on time but also in line with the quality requirements. Tight communication through emails and teleconferences has been implemented with the view to prevent any delays or any misunderstandings of the inputs and details needed.
 - Development of the communication channels and sharing of information among Partners. During kick off meeting, partners decided that the main communication channel is regular emails and the document repository is MS Teams platform. Therefore, the online shared project folder in the MS teams platform was created, with the assistance of project partner EHPA. It is regularly updated with project information; deliverables and milestones (submitted and under preparation), Task activities, minutes of meetings, timeplan and many more.
 - Organisation of Project meetings, WP Leaders meetings and Steering Committee meetings; Minutes keeping. Uploading relevant information to the MS teams folder.
- **Task 1.2 - Data Management and Ethics Requirements**
During M1 – M8, the Data Management Plan (DMP) has been developed, that outlines how the research data will be collected, processed or generated within the project. The project is fully aligned with the Open Access policy and the recommendations of the Open Research Data pilot. Furthermore, the ethics principles and requirements have been set up and are already addressed in the relevant Milestone 3.
 - **Task 1.3 – Monitoring impact of the project activities**
During M1-M8 the Environmental Footprint Guide and the Environmental Footprint Tool (EFG) were developed and uploaded in MS Teams platform. The Tool will be regularly updated by all project partners. Guidance has been given on how to input the required data.

- Deliverables and Milestones submitted
 - ✓ Milestone 1 - Consortium Agreement, CRES, M2
 - ✓ Milestone 2 - Environmental Footprint Guide, CRES, M4
 - ✓ Milestone 3 - Data and Ethics Report, CRES, M6

- Deliverables and Milestones in progress
 - Deliverable D1.2 – Technical progress report, CRES, M9
 - Deliverable D1.3 – Extract of the project data from the LIFE KPI webtool, CRES, M9.
Note: This is currently in progress. According to the official communication from the CINEA LIFE Clear Energy Transition Team, the updated version LIFE KPI webtool is expected after summer 2023.
 - Milestone 4 – Reporting of key performance indicators, CRES, M9
Note: This is currently in progress. According to the official communication from the CINEA LIFE Clear Energy Transition Team, the updated version LIFE KPI web tool is expected after summer 2023.

- Deviations, Risks
 - There are no deviations to be reported for WP1.
 - A minor deviation appeared in WP6 Task 6.2 “Online presence”. Efficient project management promptly detected this issue and appropriate mitigation measures were elaborated. The result was to minimise the risk with a minor timeplan deviation without further technical implications to the project progress. Further information is given in WP6.

1.2.2. Work package 2 Assessment of NECPs and current initiatives on RES-HC

- Overall (1 paragraph)
The activities under WP2 started in M1 (October 2022). In the past months, the WP leader, Solar Heat Europe has ensured constant coordination by means of recurring monthly meetings among the task leaders and other relevant partners (namely TRI and EnC). All tasks are proceeding well, in line with the timing of the milestones and deliverables listed in the Grant Agreement.

- Task 2.1 Assessment of NCEPs and RHC support mechanisms
The task is led by project partner Bioenergy Europe, which has performed an initial assessment of the National Renewable Energy Action Plans (NREAPs) in relation to the 2020 targets, as well as of the National Energy and Climate Plans in relation to 2030 targets. This analysis provides an overview of the measures in place at national level and assess which / if Member States have complied and are in line to comply with the EU targets for the share of renewable energy in the heating and cooling sector.
A survey gathering inputs from the NSPs panel was developed and sent. Some delays in the answers delayed partially the development of the findings, but still in line with the GA.
At the same time, project partner Energy Cities have started working on the assessment of the consistency between NECPs and actions at local level, notably through the Sustainable Energy Action Plans. This work includes the development of case studies based on relevant success stories.

- Task 2.2 Identification of main barriers and opportunities
The work under this task is ongoing. Task leader KAPE is leading the activities, in line with the timeline laid down in the Grant Agreement. KAPE is developing the PESTEL analysis for the project countries that should be available by the end of M9.

- Task 2.3 Mapping and analysis of national heating and cooling demand

The mapping was performed based on available data from Comprehensive Assessment reports from 2020 for Croatia, Germany and Portugal, while for Poland and Greece, as above-mentioned reports are missing, this task is still in progress.

Task leader EIHP is leading the mapping and analysis of national heating and cooling demand for the five target countries of the project, based on available data from the Comprehensive Assessment reports of the potential for efficient heating and cooling, which are required by the Energy Efficiency Directive. This analysis was carried out for Croatia, Germany and Portugal based on the Comprehensive Assessments from 2020. For Poland and Greece, the Comprehensive Assessment reports are missing or have not been updated, despite being a legal requirement. Therefore, EIHP will base the analysis on the reports from 2015, and then seek to find more updated data with the help of partners, national stakeholders' groups, and the EAB.

- Task 2.4 Assessing the RES-HC technology state of the art and short-term potential

The work under this task is ongoing. Task leader Solar Heat Europe is leading the activities, in line with the timeline laid down in the Grant Agreement. Solar Heat Europe is performing desk research analysing relevant deliverables from two closed EU projects (SecRHC & SecRHCII).

- Deliverables and Milestones in progress
 - M7 Review of findings with NSP and EAC (M12)
 - M8 European Workshop (M14)
 - D2.1 Renewable heating and cooling in the NECPs (M15)
 - D2.2 Report: Local initiatives for heat decarbonisation (M17)
- Deviations, Risks

No deviations and risks are reported for this period.

1.2.3. Work package 3 Development of recommendations and tools for the deployment of RES-HC

The current work under WP3 has focused on developing the methodologies and data collection templates for task 3.1 and 3.2. Trinomics has also set up periodic (initially bi-monthly and starting from June 2023 monthly) calls with the organisations in WP3 to discuss ongoing work and maintain all members informed. The more detailed summary of work undertaken under each task is provided below.

- Task 3.1 – Identifying key success factors and KPIs (Task Lead: KAPE)

Trinomics, as work package leader, has set up several calls with KAPE – Task 3.1 leaders, to develop the methodology for collecting the data required to identify key success factors (KSF) from which key performance indicators (KPIs) can be proposed. Currently, the team is refining the collection template, also based on the data collected under tasks 2.1 (NECPs assessment) and 2.2. (identification of key barriers based on PESTEL analysis) As the next step, the team will finalise the data collection template and will share it with all members of WP3 with a request for filling out the template. The collected outputs will be analysed based on a methodology being developed to identify KSFs. For each KSF identified, performance indicators will be also defined.

- Task 3.2 – Best practices, learned lessons and RHC Strategic Policy Priorities (Task Lead: Trinomics)
A call between Trinomics and Energy Cities was held on the 23rd of May to discuss the methodology for identifying best practices and lessons learned from RHC Strategic Policy Priorities. The approach was shared with CRES, as coordinators and received approval. The team is working on a collection template which, will be pre-filled with best practices identified by Energy Cities to provide concrete examples of how partners should fill the template. The template will be shared with the National Agencies for comments and approval. After the data collection step, Trinomics and Energy Cities will analyze all best practices identified to extract general best practices with broad applicability and that can support the elaboration of policy priorities.

- Task 3.3 – NECPS assessment guideline (Task Lead: EIHP)

No developments for the current reporting period.

- Task 3.4 – Development of Renewable Heat Transition Toolbox (Task Lead: DENA)

No developments for the current reporting period.

- Deliverables and Milestones in progress
 - D3.1 Key success factors for RES-HC policies (Due: M16)
 - D3.2 Strategic Policy Priorities for RES-HC (Due: M20)

- Deviations, Risks

No deviations are reported for this period.

There is a potential risk, as follows: MS9 (Development of Renewable Heat Transition Toolbox) is dependent on outputs from Tasks 3.1 and 3.2 and 3.3 but is due at the same time (M20). This timeline may not leave enough time to be able to collect all relevant outputs for developing the Renewable Heat Transition Toolbox.

1.2.4. Work package 4 Support the implementation of effective support measures for RES-HC

The WP4 - Support the implementation of effective support measures for RESHC will start at a later stage of the project implementation. The work related with the tasks identified for WP4, as described in the GA, will begin in M16 (January 2024). The main outcomes of this WP include the definition of the policy adoption scenarios for the participating countries; creation of an online knowledge sharing platform; deployment of capacity building competences aimed at relevant agents in the H&C sector and assist/support public authorities in structuring and planning RHC policies.

- Task 4.1 – Development of adoption scenarios

No developments for the current reporting period.

- Task 4.2 – Developing a knowledge sharing platform for national and local agencies

No developments for the current reporting period.

- Task 4.3 – Capacity building events

No developments for the current reporting period.

- Task 4.4 – Facilitating national implementation

No developments for the current reporting period.

- Deliverables and Milestones submitted

N.A.

- Deliverables and Milestones in progress

N.A.

- Deviations, Risks

N.A.

1.2.5. *Work package 5 Impact monitoring, evaluation and adaptation*

WP5 – Impact monitoring, evaluation and adaptation is led by EGEC and involves mainly EHP, SHE, BIO, ADENE, ENC.

- Task 5.1 – Addressing a new regulatory framework (EHP)

The work that is already in progress is listed below:

National level analysis:

- Country teams: each contributing partner chose one country of interest to lead and is engaging the national partners to perform the analysis and gather all necessary information about relevant national legislation.
- Assessment criteria scorecards: EHP finalised the assessment criteria scorecards for NECP analysis that will be used to assess the relevant national legislation.

Comparison of EU legislation

- Continuous mapping, monitoring and comparison of relevant articles: each contributing partner chose specific articles to conduct the monitoring and analysis. The comparison (2018 vs now) and analysis of the different articles is to be fed in a dedicated Excel table, once their final shape is agreed. Each contributing partner is monitoring the evolution of selected article in the meantime, informing about any important progress/change.
- SWOT analysis of the new legislation impacting H&C: A SWOT analysis will be provided for each newly agreed article. Each partner will provide a SWOT analysis for their selected articles.

The following next steps are planned:

- Finalise the national level analysis and the EU legislation comparison.
- Recommendations: once we have the final results of the negotiations, we will derive recommendations. Contributing partners will write recommendations for articles they have selected. The recommendations will be translated into policy briefs (one policy brief per article). A separate document will be created for each piece of legislation for this purpose. A policy webinar will be organised to present the results of the analysis.

- Task 5.2 – Changes to national programmes (DENA)

This Task started in March 2023 with the drafting of a first overall plan including the approach for the preparation and conception of policy live tracker to monitor and mapping changes of national programmes on the REDI4Heat website.

Subtasks already started:

- Coordination and synchronisation with relevant tasks 3.1 (identifying key success factors in NECPs) and 5.1 (addressing a new regulatory framework) and their approaches.

The following next steps are planned:

- Provision of the template for monitoring the national initiatives.
- Group meeting to coordinate monthly upload deadline.
- Meeting with relevant partners to discuss the provision of information on the website.

- Task 5.3 – Better data to monitor 2030 targets

This task will start in the second year of the project.

- Deliverables and Milestones in progress
 - D5.1 Report on RHC regulatory frame towards 2030 (M14)
- Deviations, Risks

Note: This WP anticipated its start from M5 to M2 to facilitate the partners involved in an early monitoring of the relevant EU directives revision processes as regards Task 5.1.

No deviations or risks are reported for this period.

1.2.6. Work package 6 Communication, Dissemination and Networking

WP6 – Communication, Dissemination and Networking is led by EHPA and all partners are involved. Activities implemented during this reporting period so far are briefly summarized for each task.

- Task 6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan

A Dissemination and Communication Plan (D6.1) was developed by EHPA with the support of all partners by M7; the document includes the description of the different communication phases of the project, interaction between WP6 and other work packages, characterisation of target groups and strategies to reach them out effectively, list of key stakeholders that will be targeted with ad hoc communication material, identification of communication tools, identification of international podcast to participate in, preparing news based on each partners capacity and means, definition of key communication materials to be produced, use of social media and selection of dissemination events at European and national level where the partners will participate and disseminate the REDI4Heat outcomes and messages. The Dissemination and Communication Plan also includes Communication and Dissemination KPIs, the planning of project workshops and online seminars (dates, location, content for the ones already confirmed) and it also addresses the accessibility of the project platforms until 3 years after the project ends.

The Dissemination and Communication Plan is a working-progress tool and will be periodically reviewed and updated considering new developments of the project and the same action will be considered for the monitoring of KPIs.

- Task 6.2 Online presence and project identity

In this task, the project identity has been developed through the production of the project brand guidelines, which includes the colours and fonts of the projects to be used in every communication and dissemination activities; the creation of 3 different social media accounts: LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube. LinkedIn and Twitter are already populated with contents, and they count respectively 155 followers and 23 posts published and 34 followers and 17 posts published. The website of the project has been launched in M7, with some delay respect the planned deadline of M6 because of external causes depending on the web developed in charge of the work and is considered and used as the online repository and dashboard for the stakeholders on where to find the project's info, deliverables, reports, communication, and dissemination materials, and get in contact with the consortium. Since the beginning of the project 1 newsletter in M7 has been sent to all the stakeholders interested in and the 1st of 3 promotional videos foreseen is in preparation, to provide a first visual introduction of the project to share with the general public.

- Task 6.3 Dissemination and Networking Activities

This task is focused on organising and attending dissemination events during the project lifecycle. For this task EHPA has created and shared an online repository in which all partners constantly update the dissemination activities implemented filling in a detailed template about events, publications and online activities.

At the moment, it has been organised the 1st of 3 webinars with sister projects foreseen for the project, titled “Conclusions on Fit for 55: renewable heating and cooling solutions”, the event counted in total 90 registrations and 65 participants, mainly from manufacture company, industry, university, research institute, organizations and associations focused on renewable energies. Moreover, the consortium during these first months has also participated to or organized a total of 6 different dissemination events, at local, national and international level, such as ISH Frankfurt, Euroheat & Power Congress and has already planned to participate to other 3 events in the coming months (number that is destined to grow as soon as new event date will be confirmed). In conjunction with the relevant work packages, the 1st of 4 online workshops, with public authorities to increase the understanding of RED and EED, including the new regulation is starting to be organized for M12; likewise, the 1st of 10 meetings with policy makers is also being planned.

- Task 6.4 – High level event

This task is related to the organisation of the final event in M36, so to date there are no developments in progress and updates to report.

- Deliverables and Milestones submitted
 - ✓ D6.1 – Dissemination and communication Plan (M7)
 - ✓ M18 – Online presence (M6)
- Deliverables and Milestones in progress
 - D6.2 Report on communication and dissemination activities (M36)
 - M19 High-level event (M34)

- Deviations, Risks

A minor deviation from the timeplan appeared in WP6 Task 6.2 “Online presence”. This was due to the unexpected delays of the website developer. The deviation was minor; only one month delay without any further technical implications to the project progress.

1.2.7. Work package 7 Sustainability, replication and exploitation of project results

- Overall

The WP7 - Sustainability, replication and exploitation of project results started in M6 (March 2023) and will be concluded at the end of the project implementation in M36 (September 2025). The focus of this WP and its correspondent tasks, as described in the GA, will be in the preparation, implementation and monitoring of the Sustainability, Exploitation and Replication (SE&R) Plan and on the set up and management of the European Advisory Board (EAB) and the National Stakeholders Groups (NSGs).

- Task 7.1 – Planning and monitoring SE&R

ADENE as the task leader (TL) was responsible for the completion of the current task, due in M9. The work carried out consisted of the preparation of the SE&R Plan and the definition of the monitoring structure to accompany and report on the execution of the SE&R Plan. The conclusion of the T7.1 involved a close collaboration with the coordinator (CRES) and contributions from all the consortium partners in the final revision of the report.

- Task 7.2 – Partnerships and cooperation initiatives

SHE as the TL will be responsible for the completion of T7.2. The work foreseen for this task is aligned with the implementation of the SE&R plan (T7.1) concluded in M9. In the coming months the focus will be the in the implementation of the SE&R Plan, in particular the replication and exploitation components of this plan. The planned activities include the organization of 3 seminars in non-participating countries (BE, FR and NL) and the connection/proactive approach with relevant initiatives/projects in the H&C sector.

- Task 7.3 – European Advisory Board & National Stakeholder Groups

This task relates to the formulation of the European Advisory Board (EAB) and the National Stakeholders Groups (NSG's). The constituency of the EAB was the result of the suggestions made by all the consortium partners and includes several EU experts (policy makers, RH&C experts, representatives from the NSG's, among others). As for the formulation of the NSG's, the energy agencies represented in the REDI4Heat consortium (CRES, EIHP, DENA, KAPE and ADENE) were responsible for delivering this outcome. By the end of M9, all the energy agencies had organized the first online meeting of the NSG. One member of each NSG was allocated to join the EAB. Also, the first online meeting of the EAB is planned for M10 (July 3, 2023).

- Deliverables and Milestones submitted
 - ✓ D7.1 SE&R plan (M9).
Note: At the time of writing this report, the D7.1 was already submitted.
 - ✓ MS22 NSGs and EAB constituted (M9)
- Deliverables and Milestones in progress
 - MS21 SE&R Plan (M12)
- Deviations, Risks

No deviations or risks are reported for this period.

1.3. Impact

Include in this section whether the information on section 2.1 of the DoA (how your project will contribute to the expected impacts) is still relevant or needs to be updated. Include further details in the latter case

1.3.1. What are the main achievements of the project and the main innovation activities?

The information contained in the Grant Agreement is still relevant and does not need to be updated.

Impact	Project end value	5 years beyond project end value
RES generation	11.73 GWh/year	37.97 GWh/year
GHG emissions	2664 tCO ₂ /year	8619 tCO ₂ /year
Investments in sustainable energy	4667 m€	15337 m€
Legislation and Policy	5 policy measures	30 policy measures
Increase of Skills	375 people trained	1875 people trained
Communication	4000 people reached	10000 people reached

1.3.2. What is the contribution to the state of the art?

A study carried out for the European Commission highlighted that most of the countries would not comply with the indicative target of 1.3%-point annual increase of renewables in the H&C sector established in article 23(4) of the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II).

The main goal of REDI4Heat is to support member states in implementing the provisions related to heating and cooling in the Renewable Energy Directive and to comply with the targets.

The project focuses on five target countries: Croatia, Germany, Greece, Poland, Portugal. Nevertheless, REDI4Heat also aims at having an impact in other countries. Part of the work of the project will be to focus on extending these results to other member states.

1.3.3. What are the results and impacts?

REDI4Heat will assist the target countries in identifying best practices, Key Success Factors and strategic policy priorities that will support the revision of their strategies for heating and cooling and/or NECPs, in order to increase the reference target. The impact of the project should be felt from 2023 onwards, with an increased impact towards the end of the decades.

It is extremely difficult to translate the highly political nature of REDI4Heat into concrete and measurable targets in terms of overall investment, renewable energy production triggered, reduction of greenhouse gas emissions or other desired effects.

2. Exploitation and dissemination of results

Include in this section whether the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results as described in the DoA needs to be updated and give details.

2.1. Exploitation

The exploitation plan is one of the three components of the SE&R Plan developed in the framework of WP7. The D7.1 describes the exploitation method/strategy in more detail and corresponds to the first version of the SE&R Plan. The plan will be periodically updated with new developments and initiatives, also stemming from the implementation of the SE&R and identification of opportunities to maximize the plan's impact.

The exploitation strategy is aligned with the replication strategy and will mainly address non-participating MS whose heating policies are clearly short, based on the analysis of the MS NECPs.

For this propose, 3 online seminars will be organized, aimed at a wider target audience, comprising policy-oriented actors, relevant industry and market stakeholders and national associations with whom several of the consortium trade associations have direct contact, guaranteeing a transversal approach to the H&C sector.

Also, the exploitation strategy encompasses the participation in the most relevant H&C sector events to guarantee an alignment of the policy recommendations and the market offer.

In the next reporting period, ADENE will be able to provide an overview on the KPIs (when applicable) to be achieved for the SE&R activities, as described in the D 7.1.

2.2. Dissemination

Dissemination activities are ongoing; since the beginning of the project, through the opening of the social media accounts and the launch of the website information related to the project have been promoted, engaging with the general audience and other sister projects.

Dissemination materials have been created and printed, already brought to some in person event, conferences or fairs to which partners of the consortium have participated.

Overview of the dissemination events attended and organized by the consortium and update of next events planned to participate:

Partners	Title	Type	Date	Location	Description	Status
CRES	5th Verde.tec 2023 fair and forum	Fair and Forum	17 - 19 March 2023	Athens, Greece	Presentation by Vassiliki Drosou, CRES – coordinator of the project.	Done
EHPA	ISH Frankfurt	Fair	13 - 17 March 2023	Frankfurt, Germany	Dissemination material at ISH Frankfurt - The world's largest exhibition space for the HVAC sector showcases an array of practical solutions for the most important issues of our time: achievement of climate protection targets, conservation of resources using renewable energies, increasing digitalisation and smart technologies.	Done
DENA	EnR Regular and Full Meeting	Member meeting	27- 28 March 2023	Berlin, Germany	Presentation during the Meeting among European Energy Agency, by Rita Ehrig, DENA.	Done
Bioenergy Europe	Berlin Energy Transition Dialogue (BETD)	Conference	27-28 March 2023	Berlin, Germany	Dissemination material during the BETD - From 27 to 30 March, energy sector stakeholders came together at the Berlin Energy Transition Dialogue (BETD) to advance the energy transition and offer a discussion platform. BETD provides a leading international forum for high-level representatives from governments, industry, science and civil society to share their	Done

					experiences and ideas on a safe, affordable and environmentally responsible global energy transition.	
CREs	ASTEP EU Project meeting	M36 Project meeting - Exploitation Workshop	12 May 2023	Brunel / England	Presentation at the project meeting of ASTEP UP	Done
EHPA	Conclusions on Fit for 55: renewable heating and cooling solutions	Webinar with Sister project	17 May 2023	ONLINE	1 st webinar with the sister project, RHC-ETIP, which brought together experts from the REDI4Heat Consortium to explore the impact of the legislative package on various renewable technologies. Expect to gain invaluable insights on the latest advancements and how they'll shape the European energy landscape.	Done
EHP	Euroheat & Power Congress 2023	Congress	22-24 May	Torino, Italy	Dissemination material at Euroheat & Power Congress 2023 - The 2023 edition of the International Euroheat & Power Congress has investigated the most promising pathways for District Heating & Cooling to play its part in solving the global energy & climate crisis, spurring local change for global impact.	Done
EHPA	EUSEW	Fair	20-22 June 2023	Brussels, Belgium	Dissemination material at EUSEW - The European Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW) is an annual conference organized by the European Commission and the biggest event dedicated to renewables and efficient energy use in Europe. This year the event will take place from in hybrid format, but EHPA will have a physical booth there. The theme is: "Accelerating the clean energy transition – towards lower bills and greater skills."	Planned
EHPA	Heat Pump Forum 2023	Conference	28-29 September 2023	Gare Maritime, Brussels	Dissemination material at EHPA's Heat Pump Forum 2021. About the Forum: On September 29th, EHPA celebrated its 21st anniversary while hosting the Heat Pump Forum, a hybrid event where the heat pump industry joined forces with the policy-makers as equal partners in reaching their common objectives for a green heat recovery.	Planned
EHPA	Heat Pump Summit	Conference	24-25 October 2023	Nuremberg, Germany	Dissemination of the Superhomes2030 in the context of the Heat Pump Summit. About the Heat Pump Summit: The European Heat Pump Summit is the meeting place for experts from the international heat pump sector, where prominent speakers and international decision-makers from the worlds of trade, industry and science can interact and network.	Planned

3. Success story

Will be completed at a later stage of the project – after M12

4. Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2

For each work package (WP), report and comment on any delays, reasons for them and any remedial action taken. Explain the reasons for deviations from the DoA, the consequences and the proposed corrective actions.

There are no deviations during this reporting period.

5. Deliverables

Describe the most important deliverables

The deliverables of this reporting period are

D1.2 – Technical progress report, CRES, M9

This report explains the work that has been carried out by the Project Consortium and provides an overview of the progress of the project during the first 8 months.

D6.1 – Communication & Dissemination plan, EHPA, M6

This report provides an overview on how all the communication channels and activities work together to address the identified stakeholder groups as well as to raise their awareness in the development of the project outcomes. It explains the methodology to ensure the visibility of the REDI4Heat project, the involvement of the stakeholders, as well as the maximization of the project impacts.

D7.1 – SE&R plan, ADENE, M9

This report identifies the Key Exploitable Results and presents the activities to implement within the REDI4Heat strategy to exploit these and assure the impact to a wider audience, also in a replication perspective to other MS.

6. Milestones

Describe the most important milestones

The milestones of this reporting period are

1 - Consortium Agreement, CRES, M2

This Milestone facilitates the coordination and collaboration, this model provides for internal arrangements between beneficiaries, governance of the project and financial issues.

2 - Environmental Footprint Guide, CRES, M4

This Milestone comes as a result of the Green Management attitude and incorporates the qualitative and quantitative analysis of all activities carried out during the project that can have an environmental impact. It defines the methodology and the monitoring mechanism of GHG emissions calculation.

3 - Data and Ethics Report, CRES, M6

This milestone outlines the ways in which data is collected, generated and processed throughout the lifespan of the REDI4Heat project. It also ensures that all research activities carried out under REDI4Heat project are conducted in compliance with fundamental ethical principles.

18 - Online presence, EHPA, M6

This milestone refers to the online presence of the project, namely the development of the website, the social media pages and the project visual identity.

22 - NSGs and EAB constituted, ADENE, M9

This milestone refers to the constitution of the 5 National Stakeholders Groups (EL, HR, PT, PL and DE) as well as the European Advisory Board.